

Photon Wave Equation from Continuity Equation with Poynting Vector

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Einstein's energy-momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ may be converted into the Klein-Gordon equation. This equation with $m=0$ describes a photon. P. Dirac sought an equation linear in d/dt and d/dx and developed one using matrices. There has been an interest in the literature (1) (2) to develop a similar quantum equation for the photon. It seems that the starting point for both (1) and (2) is to find a vector wave function solution to a linear d/dt , d/dx equation. In fact, (1) follows the Dirac approach, but seeks different matrices for a 3-vector than Dirac chose for a spin $1/2$ electron.

In this note, we argue that the EM continuity equation $d/dt (\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + 1/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + (1/\mu_0) \text{grad} \cdot E \times B = 0$ (no source) leads directly to a Dirac type wave equation for the photon. This equation is already linear in d/dt and d/dx and one may factor out $E - iB$. The Levi-Civita symbol ϵ_{ijk} naturally becomes the Dirac matrix for the photon as it is contained in the Poynting vector $1/\mu_0 E \times B$.

Photon Wave Function and Maxwell's Equations

It is argued in (1) that Maxwell's equations are already quantum mechanical equations for the photon (with no sources). One may take:

$$dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E \quad \text{and} \quad dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B \quad ((1))$$

And combine them to obtain one equation in $E + iB$ which is called a vector wavefunction. It may be noted that energy density $(E - iB)(E + iB)$ is the energy probability in such a case.

In (2), a Dirac approach is taken and it is postulated that:

$$i d/dt F = S \cdot (-i \text{grad}) F \quad \text{where } F \text{ is a vector wavefunction and } S, \text{ a set of 3 matrices} \quad ((2))$$

The author of (2) argues that ϵ_{ijk} (the Levi-Civita) symbol is such a set of S matrices with $\epsilon_{i(jk)}$, $\epsilon_{(jk)i}$ being the j , k th element of the i th matrix.

Photon Wave Function From the Continuity Equation

We note that the Klein-Gordon follows from a relationship between energy and momentum i.e. $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ and the idea of a wave solution $\exp(ikx - iEt)$. $-i d/dx$ of a wave solution yields p times the wave and $i d/dt$, E times the wave. Thus, one obtains:

$$d/dt d/dt W = d/dx d/dx W + m^2 W \quad \text{for a photon } m=0 \quad ((3))$$

One may argue, however, that momentum and energy are composed/created by certain fields. In EM, energy density is given by $.5\epsilon_0 E_i E_i + .5/\mu_0 B_i B_i$ and momentum density by $1/\mu_0 E_i \times B_i$. Both may be integrated over volume to give overall energy and momentum. Thus, one might wish to have a wave equation for E_i or B_i which shows some internal workings of energy and momentum of a photon.

Keeping the idea of a linear equation in d/dt and d/dx in mind, one already has such an equation in EM theory, namely the continuity equation with no sources:

$$d/dt (.5\epsilon_0 E_i E_i + .5/\mu_0 B_i B_i) + \text{grad dot } 1/\mu_0 E_i \times B_i = 0 \quad ((4))$$

From the first term on the LHS one may immediately factor out $E_i \cdot B_i$. (Using $c=1$, one may also factor out ϵ_0 because $1/(\mu_0 \epsilon_0)$ is directly related to c .)

Thus, for the first term on the LHS one has: $(E_i \cdot B_i) \text{ dot } d/dt (E_i + iB_i) \epsilon_0$

The question becomes whether one may write the second term on the LHS of ((4)) as:

$$(E_i \cdot B_i) \text{ dot } \{S \text{ dot } (-i \text{grad}) (E_i + iB_i)\} \quad ((6))$$

We note that ϵ_{ijm} appears in $E_i \times B_j$ so we use this as a choice for S . grad also appears in $E_i \times B_j$ and ((6)).

((6)) may be written as:

$$(E_i \cdot B_j) \epsilon_{ijm} (-i d_i) (E_i + B_j) \epsilon_0 = \epsilon_{ijm} (-B_j d_j E_i \epsilon_0 + E_j d_i B_m \epsilon_0) \quad ((7))$$

Here $d_i = d/dx_i$ and ϵ_{ijm} is the Levi-Civita symbol. There are no double E_i or B_j terms because ϵ_{ijm} is anti-symmetric in any two indices, but $E_i A_i B_j$ or $B_i B_j B_k$ would be symmetric rendering the combination zero.

Next, consider:

$$\text{grad dot } 1/\mu_0 E_i \times B_j = d_i [\epsilon_{ijm} E_j B_m] = \epsilon_{ijm} [(d_i E_j) B_m + E_j d_i B_m]$$

$$= -\epsilon_{imj} (d_i E_j) B_m + \epsilon_{ijm} E_j d_i B_m$$

$$= -\epsilon_{imj} (d_i E_j) B_m + \epsilon_{ijm} E_j d_i B_m \quad ((8))$$

Thus, ((7)) and ((8)) are identical and the continuity equation from electromagnetic theory represents $(E_i \cdot B_j) \text{ dot } \{ \text{photon wave equation} \}$ where the photon wave equation is:

$$i d/dt (E_i + iB_j) = S \text{ dot } (-i \text{grad}) (E_i + iB_j) \quad \text{Where } S_i(jk) = \epsilon_{ijk} \text{ and the vector wavefunction is } E_i + iB_j$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the photon wave equation is already present in the continuity equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} (.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + \text{grad} \times 1/\mu_0 E \times B = 0$$
 from electromagnetic theory. The first term may be written as $(E - iB) \frac{d}{dt} \epsilon_0 (E + iB)$. Thus, one needs to factor out $E - iB$ from the grad dot Poynting vector term. This may be done (as shown above) yielding:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} (E + iB) = S \cdot (-\text{grad}) (E + iB)$$
 where $S_i(jk) = \epsilon_{ijk}$, the Levi-Civita symbol

The Levi-Civita symbol appears in the Poynting vector $E \times B$ and so it becomes the matrix S in Dirac's representation.

We have also already noted in a previous note that for a photon E and B have the same magnitude ($c=1$) and are perpendicular. Thus, in one dimension, one may show that $\exp(ikx - i\omega t)$ is a solution of the continuity equation.

We argue that this is a direct approach to obtaining the photon wavefunction from electromagnetic theory.

References

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